

README:

The virtual machine image (Vneo4j.ova) contains all the necessary environments and tools to run our experiment. The username and password of the virtual machine are as follows:

Username: vneo4j

Password: vneo4j

The following list introduces the content in each folder:

- `~/Data/apoc-aware`: The source code of the APOC library that we modified, which applies our lifted traversal algorithm for variability-aware analysis.
- `~/Data/desugared`: The desugared source code of the five subject SPLs used in our experiments.
- `~/Data/factbase`: The factbases of our five subject SPLs. Each factbase consists of two .CSV files, one containing the nodes and the other one containing the edges of the graphical model of an SPL.
- `~/Data/Databases`: The neo4j databases of our five subject SPLs, each with their own separate folder. Each database has already been loaded with one of the subject factbases, so that users can directly run our queries after starting the database.
- `~/Data/query`: The 10 queries representing analyses of interests of our experiments, each of them is expressed in the input language of Neo4j.
- `~/Data/Rex`: The executable of variability-aware Rex.

The following instructions will walk through the process of running our experiments, using the subject SPL **AxTLS** and the **direct recursion analysis** as an example:

- Go to the folder `~/Data/Databases/axtls` and use the following command to start the database for AxTLS:
 - `bin/neo4j start`
- You will see the following output:

```
vneo4j@ubuntu:~/Data/Databases/axtls$ bin/neo4j start
Directories in use:
home:           /home/vneo4j/Data/Databases/axtls
config:         /home/vneo4j/Data/Databases/axtls/conf
logs:          /home/vneo4j/Data/Databases/axtls/logs
plugins:        /home/vneo4j/Data/Databases/axtls/plugins
import:         /home/vneo4j/Data/Databases/axtls/import
data:           /home/vneo4j/Data/Databases/axtls/data
certificates:  /home/vneo4j/Data/Databases/axtls/certificates
licenses:      /home/vneo4j/Data/Databases/axtls/licenses
run:            /home/vneo4j/Data/Databases/axtls/run
Starting Neo4j.
WARNING: Max 4096 open files allowed, minimum of 40000 recommended. See the Neo4j manual.
Started neo4j (pid:16996). It is available at http://localhost:7471
There may be a short delay until the server is ready.
vneo4j@ubuntu:~/Data/Databases/axtls$
```

- Wait for a few seconds and use the following command to open the cypher shell:
 - `bin/cypher-shell -a neo4j://localhost:7681`
- The usernames and passwords of the cypher shells for all our five SPLs are the same:
 - **Username: neo4j**
 - **Password: vneo4j**

- If you see the following output, it means that you have successfully opened the cypher shell:

```
vneo4j@ubuntu:~/Data/Databases/axtls$ bin/cypher-shell -a neo4j://localhost:7681
username: neo4j
password: *****
Connected to Neo4j using Bolt protocol version 4.3 at neo4j://localhost:7681 as user neo4j.
Type :help for a list of available commands or :exit to exit the shell.
Note that Cypher queries must end with a semicolon.
neo4j@neo4j>
```

- Next, you will be able to run the queries. Let's use the direct recursion query as an example. Go to the folder ~/Data/query, copy the contents of the file Direct Recursion.txt to the cypher shell, and click Enter to run the query:

```
neo4j@neo4j> WITH "MATCH (srcFunc:cFunction)
CALL apoc.aware.path.expandConfig(srcFunc, {
  relationshipFilter: 'call>',
  labelFilter: '>cFunction',
  minLevel: 1,
  maxLevel:1
})
YIELD path
WITH path, last(nodes(path)) AS dstFunc
WHERE srcFunc.id = dstFunc.id
RETURN path" AS query
CALL apoc.export.csv.query(query, "neo4j-directRecursion-aware.csv", {})
YIELD file, source, format, nodes, relationships, properties, time, rows, batchSize, batches, done, data
RETURN file, source, format, nodes, relationships, properties, time, rows, batchSize, batches, done, data;
```

file	source	format	nodes	relationships	properties	time	rows	batchSize	batches	done	data
"neo4j-directRecursion-aware.csv"	"statement: cols(1)"	"csv"	0	0	5	313	5	20000	1	TRUE	NULL

```
1 row
ready to start consuming query after 119 ms, results consumed after another 557 ms
neo4j@neo4j>
```

- The result will be saved inside the import folder of the corresponding database.
- If you want to close the cypher shell, you could type in:
 - :exit

```
neo4j@neo4j> :exit
Bye!
vneo4j@ubuntu:~/Data/Databases/axtls$
```

- Remember to also stop the Neo4j database if you finish running the query for the subject system using:
 - bin/neo4j stop

```
vneo4j@ubuntu:~/Data/Databases/axtls$ bin/neo4j stop
Stopping Neo4j..... stopped.
```

Note that the process of running the queries for each subject system is the same, except for the port number of opening the cypher shell. Below is the list of the commands (including the port number) for opening the cypher shell for each of the SPLs:

- AxTLS: bin/cypher-shell -a neo4j://localhost:7681
- Toybox: bin/cypher-shell -a neo4j://localhost:7682

We use argument `-c` to extract the factbase for a subject system to be loaded into the lifted Neo4j engine. If you are interested, we provide the desugared source code for our subject systems, so that you could use the following instruction to extract the factbases for each of the subject systems:

```
./Rex -N "ENABLE*" <folder containing source code> -c <node.csv>  
<edge.csv> 2>error.txt
```

For example, if you want to extract the factbase for AxTLS, you could use the following command:

```
./Rex -N "ENABLE*" /home/vneo4j/Data/desugared/axtls -c node.csv  
edge.csv 2>error.txt
```

The generated two `.csv` files, `node.csv` and `edge.csv` comprises the factbase that can be loaded into Neo4j.